

The Relationship of Mediterranean Diet Compliance with Metabolic Parameters, Obesity Markers and Inflammation in Women with Abdominal Obesity

Abdominal Obeziteli Kadınlarda Akdeniz Diyetine Uyumun Metabolik Parametreler, Obezite Belirteçleri ve İnflamasyonla İlişkisi

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ABSTRACT

Aim: This study aimed to investigate the relationship between Mediterranean diet adherence and various metabolic, inflammatory and oxidative stress markers in women with and without abdominal obesity.

Material and Method: A total of 68 women aged 18–50 years participated in the study, including 34 women with abdominal obesity and 34 women without abdominal obesity. Anthropometric measurements, biochemical parameters and adherence to the Mediterranean Diet were assessed using the Mediterranean Diet Adherence Scale (MEDAS). Peptides, inflammatory markers and oxidative stress parameters were measured using the ELISA method.

Results: Women with abdominal obesity had significantly higher levels of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), liver enzymes, C-reactive protein (CRP), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6) and an unfavorable lipid profile. They also had lower plasma antioxidant levels and MEDAS scores. Peptide analysis showed reduced levels of adropin, obestatin (OB), ghrelin (GH) and nesfatin-1, but an increased GH/OB ratio. A negative correlation was found between MEDAS scores and HOMA-IR, cholesterol, triglycerides and low-density lipoproteins (LDL). Positive correlations were observed between MEDAS scores and levels of adropin, obestatin and antioxidant parameters. TNF- α and IL-6 were negatively correlated with MEDAS scores.

Conclusion: Abdominal obesity in young women is associated with increased metabolic risk. Adherence to the Mediterranean diet has a protective role by reducing inflammation and oxidative stress, thus emphasizing its importance in dietary interventions aimed at metabolic health.

Keywords: Abdominal obesity, Mediterranean diet, adropin, ghrelin/obestatin, nesfatin-1, inflammation

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu çalışmanın amacı, abdominal obezitesi olan ve olmayan kadınlarda Akdeniz diyetine uyum ile çeşitli metabolik, inflamatuvar ve oksidatif stres belirteçleri arasındaki ilişkiyi değerlendirmektir.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Çalışmaya yaşları 18–50 arasında değişen 68 kadın katılmıştır. Bunlardan 34'ü abdominal obezitesi olan 34'ü ise abdominal obezitesi olmayan bireylerdir. Antropometrik ölçümler, biyokimyasal parametreler ve Akdeniz Diyeti Uyum Ölçeği (MEDAS) ile diyet uyumu değerlendirilmiştir. Peptitler, inflamatuvar belirteçler ve oksidatif stres parametreleri ELISA yöntemiyle ölçülmüştür.

Bulgular: Abdominal obezitesi olan kadınlarda insülin direnci (HOMA-IR), karaciğer enzimleri, C-reaktif protein (CRP), tümör nekroz faktörü alfa (TNF- α), interlökin-6 (IL-6) düzeyleri ve olumsuz lipid profili anlamlı olarak daha yüksek bulunmuştur. Ayrıca bu grupta plazma antioksidan düzeyleri ve MEDAS skorlarının daha düşük olduğu görülmüştür. Adropin, obestatin (OB), ghrelin (GH) ve nesfatin-1 düzeylerinde azalma; GH/OB oranında ise artış saptanmıştır. Her iki grupta da HOMA-IR, kolesterol, trigliserit ve düşük yoğunluklu lipoprotein (LDL) ile MEDAS skorları arasında negatif korelasyon bulunmuştur. Adropin, obestatin ve antioksidan düzeyleri ile MEDAS skorları arasında pozitif; TNF- α ve IL-6 ile negatif korelasyon saptanmıştır.

Sonuç: Genç kadınlarda abdominal obezite metabolik hastalık riskini artırmaktadır. Anti-inflamatuvar ve antioksidan özelliklere sahip olan Akdeniz diyeti, abdominal obezitenin ve ilişkili metabolik risklerin azaltılmasında önemli bir rol oynamaktadır. Bu yönüyle klinik beslenme müdahalelerinde dikkate alınmalıdır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Abdominal obezite, Akdeniz diyeti, adropin, ghrelin/obestatin, nesfatin-1, inflamasyon

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INTRODUCTION

Obesity, defined as excessive fat accumulation affecting health, results from genetic and environmental factors (1,2). While BMI is commonly used for classifying obesity, it does not reflect fat distribution. Therefore, WHO suggests waist circumference and waist-hip ratio in addition to BMI (3). Excess fat impacts insulin sensitivity, inflammation, oxidative status, and increases the risk for noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), especially when distributed viscerally (4).

According to the Turkish Endocrinology and Metabolism Association (TEMED), abdominal obesity is defined as waist circumference ≥ 100 cm in men and ≥ 90 cm in women, with a prevalence of 53% in Turkey (5). Abdominal obesity is closely associated with metabolic syndrome and related disorders such as dyslipidemia, glucose intolerance, hypertension, and inflammation (6, 7). Adipokines like adiponectin, leptin, TNF- α and IL-6 produced by abdominal fat contribute to cardiovascular disease risk (8).

Healthy lifestyle changes, particularly increased consumption of fruits, vegetables, whole grains and healthy fats, are recommended for NCD prevention (9). The Mediterranean diet is a key model in preventing NCD-related morbidity and mortality, including obesity (10).

Adropin regulates energy homeostasis and metabolic functions (11); ghrelin influences appetite (12); obestatin, with opposing action to ghrelin, suppresses appetite (13); and nesfatin-1 promotes satiety and weight loss (14).

It was proposed that adherence to the Mediterranean diet may confer a protective influence on specific regulatory peptides such as adropin, ghrelin, and nesfatin-1 that are implicated in insulin resistance, inflammatory processes, and oxidative stress among women with abdominal obesity. Few studies have examined the Mediterranean diet's relationship with abdominal obesity, insulin resistance and inflammation, especially in young women. Also this study is the first to assess the Mediterranean diet's correlation with metabolic, inflammatory, oxidative markers, and regulatory peptides (adropin, obestatin, ghrelin, nesfatin-1) in women with and without abdominal obesity. Given its focus on healthy individuals, the study aims to contribute significantly to early detection and prevention of metabolic disorders.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

All participants provided written informed consent, and the study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Amasya University (28/02/2020-E-5735).

Study Design and Population

This prospective study included 68 women (25–50 y): 34 with abdominal obesity (waist ≥ 90 cm) and 34 without abdominal obesity (waist < 90 cm) who attended Amasya Gümüşhacıköy State Hospital. Exclusion criteria were pregnancy or lactation, smoking, alcohol abuse, any medication/supplement use, or diagnosed metabolic/chronic illness (e.g., advanced DM, CVD, renal failure).

Anthropometry (waist, height, weight) and body composition were measured with TANITA MC-580 BIA device. Adherence to the Mediterranean diet was evaluated using the 14-item Mediterranean Diet Adherence Screener (MEDAS), developed by Martinez-Gonzalez et al. (15) and validated in Turkey by Pehlivanoğlu, Balcıoğlu and Ünlüoğlu (16). The screener includes questions on food consumption frequency and habits aligned with Mediterranean diet principles.

Venous blood samples were collected from all participants after an overnight fast of 12 hours, between 08:00 and 08:30 a.m., outside of menstrual periods. Routine biochemical parameters were analyzed immediately. Serum samples designated for ELISA-based measurements of adropin, obestatin, ghrelin, nesfatin-1, TNF- α , and IL-6 (SUNRED Biological Technology, Shanghai, China), as well as for total antioxidant status (Rel Assay Diagnostics, Gaziantep, Turkey), were aliquoted and stored at -70 °C until analysis. The study was financially supported by the Amasya University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit (Project No: FMB-BAP 20-0434).

Statistical Analysis

Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median (interquartile range, IQR) for continuous variables, and as percentages for categorical variables. Normality of distribution was assessed prior to analysis. For continuous variables, Student's t-test was applied in cases of normal distribution, while the Mann-Whitney U test was used when distributional assumptions were not met. Associations between categorical variables were analyzed using Pearson's or Spearman's χ^2 tests, as appropriate. All analyses were conducted using SPSS software (version 26, IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA), with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The mean age was 34.76 ± 5.7 in the control group and 40.15 ± 6.32 in the abdominal obesity group. ROC analysis determined MEDAS cutoff scores of 6 for abdominal obesity (waist > 90 cm) and 5 for obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²), optimizing sensitivity and specificity. Logistic

regression showed that MEDAS scores <6 and <5 were associated with 2.5-fold and 2-fold increased risks for abdominal obesity and obesity, respectively (OR 2; 95% CI 2.37-7.01).

HOMA-IR was calculated as: $\text{HOMA-IR} = (\text{Fasting glucose [mg/dL]} \times \text{Fasting insulin } [\mu\text{U/mL}]) / 405$.

Table 1. Binary comparison of study groups in terms of MEDAS, anthropometric measurements and biochemical parameters.

	Mean±SD		p
	Control group (n=34)	Abdominal obesity group (n=34)	
MEDAS	8.29±1.16	3.88±1.20	<0.001 ^{a**}
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.57±2.81	34.90±7.21	<0.001 ^{a**}
Waist circumference (cm)	71.76±4.03	103.15±12.35	<0.001 ^{a**}
Fat mass (%)	28.92±4.72	40.15±5.59	<0.001 ^{b**}
Visceral fat rating	3.53±1.42	9.88±4.07	<0.001 ^{a**}
Glucose (mg/dl)	93.53±10.77	98.85±12.65	0.018 ^{a*}
Insulin(mIU/l)	7.89±3.05	12.63±3.55	<0.001 ^{b**}
HOMA-IR	1.83±0.75	3.09±0.95	<0.001 ^{a**}
%HbA1c	5.23±0.26	5.86±1.00	<0.001 ^{b**}
ALT (IU/l)	15.76±8.85	19.32±12.37	0.042 ^{a*}
AST (IU/l)	16.35±5.22	17.50±6.33	0.453 ^a
AST/ALT ratio	1.19±0.44	1.00±0.25	0.026 ^{b*}
GGT (IU/L)	14.76±6.38	21.97±17.66	0.031 ^{a*}
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	162.74±26.92	186.91±31.90	0.001 ^{a**}
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	75.00±35.62	130.38±77.77	<0.001 ^{b**}
HDL (mg/dl)	58.15±13.88	48.34±10.27	0.003 ^{a**}
LDL (mg/dl)	89.58±30.52	112.49±29.27	0.002 ^{a**}
Adropin (pg/ml)	0.39±0.13	0.17±0.06	<0.001 ^{b**}
Obestatin (ng/ml)	10.21±2.06	3.79±1.88	<0.001 ^{a**}
Ghrelin (ng/ml)	2.38±0.67	1.76±0.53	0.011 ^{b*}
GH/OB ratio	0.24±0.08	0.58±0.31	<0.001 ^{a**}
Nesfatin-1 (mmol/L)	13.48±4.59	5.43±1.96	<0.001 ^{a**}
CRP	3.34±7.71	6.67±6.41	<0.001 ^{a**}
TNF-α (ng/ml)	184.74±41.42	431.10±98.22	0.033 ^{b*}
IL-6(ng/ml)	75.14±24.10	167.15±49.02	<0.001 ^{a**}
TAS(mmol trolox equival./L)	1.36±0.34	0.78±0.25	<0.001 ^{b**}

aStudent's t-test (data follow a normal distribution), bMann Whitney U (data follow a non-normal distribution), *(p<0.05), **(p<0.01)

Compared to controls, the abdominal obesity group had significantly higher levels of: waist circumference, BMI, fat mass, visceral fat rating, insulin, HOMA-IR, HbA1c, total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, CRP, IL-6, TNF-α, fasting glucose, ALT, GGT and ghrelin/obestatin ratio.

The control group showed significantly higher: MEDAS scores, HDL, adropin, obestatin, nesfatin-1, TAS, ghrelin, AST/ALT ratio (p<0.01 or p<0.05 where indicated; see **Table 1** for detailed values). These findings reinforce the inverse relationship between Mediterranean diet adherence and obesity-related metabolic and inflammatory markers.

According to **Table 2**, in the control group, waist circumference is strongly and positively correlated with BMI, fat mass, visceral fat, fasting insulin, HOMA-IR, GGT, LDL and IL-6, while showing inverse associations with MEDAS score, HDL and obestatin. BMI exhibits similar positive links to insulin resistance, liver enzymes, lipids, visceral fat and IL-6 but negative links to MEDAS, HDL, adropin, obestatin, ghrelin and TAS. Higher MEDAS scores correlate negatively with insulin, HOMA-IR, LDL, GGT, TNF-α, IL-6, total cholesterol and the ghrelin/obestatin ratio, yet positively with adropin, obestatin, TAS and HDL.

In abdominal obesity group, waist circumference and BMI display robust positive correlations with HOMA-IR, GGT, visceral adiposity, fasting glucose, insulin, total cholesterol, LDL, GH/OB, CRP, TNF-α and IL-6 and strong negative correlations with MEDAS score, adropin, obestatin, nesfatin-1, TAS and the AST/ALT ratio. Conversely, higher MEDAS scores are linked to lower insulin resistance, liver enzymes, lipids, adiposity indices and inflammatory markers, while associating positively with adropin, obestatin, nesfatin-1, HDL, AST/ALT and TAS. These patterns underscore that greater Mediterranean-diet adherence aligns with more favorable metabolic, oxidative and inflammatory profiles, whereas increasing adiposity intensifies metabolic and inflammatory derangements in both cohorts (see **Table 2** for detailed values).

According to **Table 3**, adropin, the ghrelin/obestatin (GH/OB) ratio and nesfatin-1 exhibit distinct metabolic and inflammatory correlates. In the control group, higher adropin concentrations are strongly associated with greater total antioxidant status, whereas they relate inversely to fasting insulin, HOMA-IR, IL-6, GGT, LDL, total cholesterol, TNF-α and the GH/OB ratio; they correlate positively with HDL. The GH/OB ratio itself rises with total cholesterol and LDL. Nesfatin-1 shows a modest positive association with the AST/ALT ratio.

In abdominal-obesity group, adropin retains favourable links—positively correlating with nesfatin-1, HDL and AST/ALT, while inversely correlating with the GH/OB ratio, insulin, HOMA-IR, GGT, LDL, total cholesterol, CRP, IL-6 and body-fat percentage. Conversely, a higher GH/OB ratio corresponds to greater insulin resistance (insulin, HOMA-IR), CRP elevations and lower nesfatin-1 and AST/ALT. Nesfatin-1 itself tracks positively with AST/ALT but inversely with insulin, HOMA-IR, GGT, CRP, TNF-α and adiposity.

Collectively, these data indicate that elevated adropin and nesfatin-1—and a lower GH/OB ratio—align with more favourable metabolic, hepatic and inflammatory profiles, particularly in women with abdominal obesity (see **Table 3** for detailed statistics).

Table 2. Correlation of waist circumference, BMI and MEDAS with some metabolic parameters, inflammation parameters and body composition in study groups

	Waist circumference				BMI				MEDAS							
	r		p		r		p		r		p					
	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity				
Waist circumference	1															
BMI	.764**	.957**	<0.001	<0.001	1											
MEDAS	-.398*	-.738**	0.020	<0.001	-.556**	-.766**	0.001	<0.001	1							
Fat mass	.668**	.931**	<0.001	<0.001	.547**	.939**	0.001	<0.001	-0.092	-.689**	0.606	<0.001				
Visceral fat rating	.758**	.783**	<0.001	<0.001	.583**	.776**	<0.001	<0.001	-0.316	-.517**	0.069	0.002				
Glucose	0.153	.505**	0.388	0.002	0.090	.502**	0.612	0.002	0.156	-.356*	0.379	0.039				
Insulin	.355*	.535**	0.040	0.001	.594**	.572**	<0.001	<0.001	-.647**	-.617**	<0.001	<0.001				
HOMA-IR	.381*	.698**	0.026	<0.001	.589**	.732**	<0.001	<0.001	-.562**	-.703**	0.001	<0.001				
AST/ALT	0.122	-.484**	0.493	0.004	-0.165	-.454**	0.352	0.007	0.109	.458**	0.538	0.006				
GGT	.384*	.620**	0.025	<0.001	.435*	.691**	0.010	<0.001	-.628**	-.575**	<0.001	<0.001				
Total cholesterol	0.329	.429*	0.057	0.011	.380*	.533**	0.026	0.001	-.509**	-.475**	0.002	0.005				
HDL	-.366*	-0.217	0.033	0.217	-.542**	-0.207	0.001	0.240	.508**	0.273*	0.002	0.019				
LDL	.403*	.420*	0.018	0.013	.548**	.528**	0.001	0.001	-.625**	-.440**	<0.001	0.009				
Adropin	-0.260	-.545**	0.138	0.001	-.390*	-.509**	0.023	0.002	.848**	.730**	<0.001	<0.001				
Obestatin	-.380*	-.442**	0.027	0.009	-.398*	-.427*	0.020	0.012	.769**	.739**	<0.001	<0.001				
Ghrelin	-0.281	0.175	0.108	0.322	-.373*	0.091	0.030	0.609	0.109	-0.208	0.538	0.238				
GH/OB	-0.044	.411*	0.804	0.016	-0.126	.363*	0.477	0.035	-.379*	-.638**	0.027	<0.001				
Nesfatin-1	0.190	-.571**	0.283	<0.001	0.027	-.536**	0.881	0.001	0.226	.790**	0.199	<0.001				
CRP	-0.090	.548**	0.611	0.001	-0.092	.509**	0.603	0.002	0.213	-.506**	0.226	0.002				
TNF- α	0.197	.461**	0.264	0.006	.448**	.414*	0.008	0.015	-.599**	-.442**	<0.001	0.009				
IL-6	.349*	.392*	0.043	0.022	.593**	.381*	p<0.001	0.026	-.684**	-.434*	<0.001	0.010				
TAS	-0.199	-.353*	0.260	0.041	-.363*	-.381*	0.035	0.026	.703**	.436**	<0.001	0.010				

*(p<0.05), **(p<0.01)

Table 3. Correlation of adropin, GH/OB ratio and nesfatin-1 levels with some metabolic parameters, inflammatory parameters and body composition in study groups

	Adropin				GH/OB				Nesfatin-1							
	r		p		r		p		r		p					
	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity	Control	Abdominal obesity				
Adropin	1															
GH/OB	-.416*	-.612**	0.014	<0.001	1											
Nesfatin-1	0.207	.635**	0.241	<0.001	-0.222	-.721**	0.207	<0.001	1							
Insulin	-.602**	-.407*	<0.001	0.017	0.302	.523**	0.083	0.001	-0.095	-.490**	0.594	0.003				
HOMAIR	-.541**	-.458**	0.001	0.006	0.302	.445**	0.083	0.008	-0.124	-.509**	0.483	0.002				
AST/ALT	0.172	.424*	0.331	0.013	-0.066	-.373*	0.710	0.030	.354*	.464**	0.040	0.006				
GGT	-.519**	-.371*	0.002	0.031	0.275	0.216	0.115	0.219	-0.129	-.420*	0.466	0.013				
Total cholesterol	-.357*	-.401*	0.038	0.019	.388*	0.136	0.023	0.442	-0.260	-0.191	0.138	0.280				
HDL	.469**	.347*	0.005	0.044	0.034	-0.115	0.849	0.517	-0.090	0.049	0.612	0.781				
LDL	-.478**	-.388*	0.004	0.024	.340*	0.159	0.049	0.368	-0.273	-0.219	0.118	0.213				
CRP	0.192	-.549**	0.277	0.001	0.093	.401*	0.603	0.019	-0.184	-.489**	0.297	0.003				
TNF- α	-.521**	-0.333	0.002	0.055	-0.118	0.194	0.507	0.272	-0.132	-.360*	0.458	0.037				
IL-6	-.623**	-.353*	<0.001	0.041	0.165	0.320	0.350	0.065	-0.153	-0.260	0.386	0.138				
TAS	.619**	0.111	<0.001	0.533	-0.189	-0.317	0.285	0.068	0.086	0.291	0.627	0.095				
Fat mass	0.036	-.498**	0.840	0.003	-0.105	0.316	0.554	0.069	0.170	-.479**	0.336	0.004				

*(p<0.05) **(p<0.01)

DISCUSSION

While the Mediterranean diet (MD) has been widely examined for its general anti-obesity effects, limited research has specifically addressed its relationship with abdominal obesity. Our findings support existing literature indicating MD's beneficial impact on BMI and waist circumference (17). In our study, individuals with abdominal obesity showed increased levels of insulin resistance (IR), HbA1c, liver enzymes (ALT, AST/ALT, GGT) and unfavorable lipid profiles (elevated TG, LDL, total cholesterol; reduced HDL). Additionally, inflammatory markers (CRP, TNF- α , IL-6) were elevated, while TAS levels were lower. MEDAS scores were significantly lower in women with abdominal obesity, suggesting poor adherence to MD.

This is consistent with findings from Careggi University Hospital, where low MD adherence was associated with a 3.5-fold increase in abdominal obesity risk (18). Another study of 4388 adults found each unit increase in MEDAS score correlated with a decrease in BMI and waist circumference (19). Similarly, in the PREDIMED study involving 5821 individuals, MD groups had lower abdominal obesity and hyperglycemia incidence over 4.8 years (20). A large Spanish trial confirmed small yet consistent reductions in anthropometric markers among MD followers (21). In our cohort, greater adherence to MD was associated with lower fasting insulin, glucose, and HOMA-IR scores. This supports cross-sectional findings from 4700 adults where high MD adherence predicted better glycemic and anthropometric parameters (22).

Lipid levels improved with adherence: total cholesterol and LDL decreased, HDL increased. GGT levels dropped significantly in both groups, and the AST/ALT ratio improved in women with abdominal obesity. These trends are supported by a meta-analysis involving 705 participants (23) and a systematic review on NAFLD patients (24,25).

Inflammatory and oxidative markers followed similar patterns. CRP and TNF- α levels were inversely associated with MEDAS score, and TAS showed a positive correlation. In the Attica study, CRP and IL-6 were 20% and 17% lower, respectively, in participants with high MD adherence (26).

Our analysis showed positive correlations between adropin and MEDAS scores in both groups. This is in agreement with controlled trials showing diets high in saturated fat and sugar reduced serum adropin levels (27). A recent systematic review and meta-analysis involving 643 participants demonstrated significantly lower circulating adropin levels in individuals with overweight and obesity compared to normal-weight controls, supporting the association between reduced adropin and adverse metabolic

status (29). Nesfatin-1 levels also positively correlated with MD adherence and were significantly lower in women with abdominal obesity. Similar observations were reported in myocardial infarction patients (30) and healthy female participants (46). Obestatin levels increased with MD adherence, while ghrelin levels showed no significant trend. However, the ghrelin/obestatin ratio declined with adherence. A study on 1495 overweight/obese adults in Spain linked higher ghrelin and poor MD adherence to weight loss resistance (31). This ratio has also been shown to relate to BMI and lipid metabolism.

Our findings may also be explained through possible biochemical mechanisms of the Mediterranean diet. Polyphenols in extra virgin olive oil have been shown to inhibit NF- κ B signaling and reduce TNF- α and IL-6 levels, thereby improving insulin sensitivity (32). Similarly, omega-3 fatty acids activate PPAR pathways, enhancing lipid oxidation and modulating adipokine secretion. These mechanisms could partly explain the observed improvements in HOMA-IR and lipid profile. Moreover, modulation of inflammatory pathways may help restore the balance between orexigenic and anorexigenic signals, reflected in a lower ghrelin/obestatin ratio, thus linking Mediterranean diet adherence with better appetite regulation and metabolic outcomes (38, 39).

BMI and waist circumference were strongly linked to HOMA-IR, fasting glucose and insulin levels, particularly in women with abdominal obesity. A Chinese study of 1834 adults confirmed the correlation between visceral fat and IR even among those with normal waist circumference (40).

Lipid data from Ecuador showed that women with abdominal obesity were more likely to have diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and hypertriglyceridemia (41). Similarly, increased waist circumference was significantly associated with a higher atherogenic index in a Chinese sample (42).

Plasma TNF- α and IL-6 levels were approximately twice as high in women with abdominal obesity. Literature confirms their positive association with BMI and waist circumference (39, 40). Finally, adropin levels were inversely associated with BMI and waist circumference in women with abdominal obesity. This finding is in line with a recent systematic review and meta-analysis including 643 participants, which demonstrated that circulating adropin concentrations are significantly lower in overweight and obese individuals compared to those of normal weight (29). These results reinforce the notion that reduced adropin may contribute to the pathophysiology of obesity through its links to insulin resistance, dysregulated energy homeostasis, and adverse cardiometabolic outcomes.

Ghrelin and obestatin were significantly altered in women with abdominal obesity. A meta-analysis found higher ghrelin and obestatin in normal-weight individuals (42), suggesting that their balance, particularly the ghrelin/obestatin ratio, may be crucial in appetite and energy regulation (43, 44, 45).

In our study, we observed an increase in the GH/OB ratio and a negative correlation with MEDAS scores. This finding suggests that in obese individuals, orexigenic signals (ghrelin) become dominant, while anorexigenic signals such as obestatin are relatively diminished. The literature has emphasized that the GH/OB ratio is a critical biomarker of appetite regulation and energy homeostasis. For instance, İbrahim et al. (2018) reported that the ghrelin/obestatin ratio is associated with body mass index and lipid metabolism. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2008) highlighted that the GH/OB ratio reflects the imbalance between appetite-stimulating and appetite-suppressing pathways, playing an important role in the pathophysiology of obesity. These results are consistent with our findings and suggest that Mediterranean diet adherence may exert a protective influence on this hormonal balance (33, 34).

Nesfatin-1 levels were also lower in women with abdominal obesity. This is supported by previous studies showing negative associations between nesfatin-1 and body fat percentage, BMI and glucose levels (14, 46).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the Mediterranean diet appears to be a protective dietary pattern against abdominal obesity and its metabolic consequences. Our study confirms its beneficial role in improving inflammatory, glycemic, lipid, hormonal, and oxidative stress parameters. Adherence to MD was linked to lower waist circumference, better insulin sensitivity, improved liver enzymes, and favorable hormone profiles, including increased adropin, obestatin, and nesfatin-1 levels. The study also demonstrated that women with abdominal obesity had significantly lower MD adherence scores, reinforcing the association between poor diet and metabolic dysfunction.

This is the first study conducted in the Central Black Sea region of Turkey to examine the relationship between MEDAS scores and detailed metabolic and hormonal parameters. By controlling for age and comorbidities, the study provides a clearer picture of abdominal obesity's direct metabolic impact. Notably, individuals with low MD adherence had a 2.5-fold increased risk of abdominal obesity (waist >90 cm) compared to a 2-fold risk for general obesity (BMI >30 kg/m²), suggesting that waist circumference may be a more sensitive indicator of MD-related metabolic risk.

Limitations

This study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, due to its cross-sectional design, the findings indicate associations rather than causal relationships. Second, the analyses were conducted on a relatively small sample of 68 women, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Third, the study included only female participants, making it difficult to extrapolate the findings to men. Finally, although the evaluation of novel biomarkers such as adropin and nesfatin-1 provides an important contribution to the literature, other potentially relevant adipokines (e.g., leptin, adiponectin) were not assessed, which could have offered a more comprehensive understanding of metabolic regulation.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: The study was conducted with the approval of the Amasya University Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Date: 28/02/2020; Decision No: 5735).

Informed Consent: All patients signed the free and informed consent form.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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